

1975

Council on Library Resources, Inc.
nineteenth annual report

The Council on Library Resources, Inc., is a private operating foundation incorporated in the District of Columbia with the principal objective of aiding in the solution of library problems. The Council, whose Members also constitute its Board of Directors, maintains its offices in Washington, D. C.

The Council was established in 1956 at the instance of the Ford Foundation with a grant of five million dollars, to be expended over a five-year period, "for the purpose of aiding in the solution of problems of libraries generally and of research libraries in particular, conducting research in, developing and demonstrating new techniques and methods, and disseminating through any means the results thereof, and for making grants to other institutions and persons for such purposes; and for providing leadership in and wherever appropriate, coordination of efforts (1) to develop the resources and services of libraries and (2) to improve relations between American and foreign libraries and archives." The Council does not assist individual libraries in meeting normal requirements for buildings, collections, or staff.

In 1960, 1967, 1971, and again in 1974 the Ford Foundation approved new grants totaling twenty-four million dollars to enable the Council to carry forward its programs of research and demonstration toward the solution of library problems.

The Council conducts its work through directly administered programs as well as grants to and contracts with other appropriate organizations or individuals. It welcomes proposals for work in furtherance of its objectives.

19th annual report

for the year ending June 30, 1975

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table of contents

Background of Council	inside front cover
Members of the Council and of the Board of Directors	4
Council Committees and Officers	5
Council Staff	6
The Year 1974-75	7
Automation and National Library Services'	9
Professional Development	17
Management	23
Preservation and Microforms	26
Improving Services to Users	31
International Activities	36
General	40
Publications Resulting from CLR-Supported Programs, Fellowships	41
Summary of CLR-Supported Projects Active in Fiscal 1975	44
Financial Statements	50
Index of Grants	56
Acknowledgements	inside back cover

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¹ Miss Ackerman, Dr. Davis, Mr. Haas, and Mr. Kempner were elected to the Council Board on November 2, 1974.

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² Mr. Butterfield succeeded Dr. Brooks on November 2, 1974.

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³ Mrs. Hill resigned in June, 1975, and was replaced by Mr. Tew.

⁴ As of April, 1975.

⁵ Until his retirement March 31, 1975, when he became a consultant.

the year 1974-75

Recently opportunities have arisen for the Council on Library Resources to play a more active part than formerly in the effort to help libraries. Many of these opportunities have been in the area of networks and national library services where, with the cooperation of those it serves, CLR has helped to bring together the work of individual institutions and organizations in the interest of a common goal.

These are important programs and appropriate activities for the Council. But the programs that please us most are those we have initiated to assist libraries through providing opportunities for librarians to broaden their experience while developing their skills. The first of these was the CLR Fellowship Program; then came the Academic Library Management Intern Program, and this year the Council's board of directors approved an Advanced Study Program to help qualified librarians receive the graduate training they need to become subject specialists in academic and research libraries.

We have heard that these programs are of considerable benefit to the librarians involved and to libraries in general. It should be noted, however, that the Council has also profited greatly from the experience. Through these programs we have come to know well a cross section of the library community. We have been privileged to share the thoughts of many of this diverse group on where they think libraries are going and how they should get there. And it is with great satisfaction that we have followed the advancing careers of former CLR Fellows and Interns.

None of this, of course, would be possible without the unstinting cooperation of many people and institutions—the directors of the home libraries of the CLR Fellows, Interns, or Scholars who provide the necessary leaves of absence; busy library directors who take on management interns and allow CLR Fellows to visit; and scores of other librarians who give of their time to help screen and make decisions on the many applications that come to us for each program. The selflessness of these people exemplifies the service commitment of librarians we too often take for granted.

This seems an appropriate place and time to say, "Thank you."

FRED C. COLE
President

automation and national library services

Approximately 40 percent of the Council's program funds are allocated to activities, including those in automation and networking, that will lead to the development of national library services. The size of that percentage reflects not only the costs involved in making computers work for libraries, but also the essential nature of this activity in attaining the goal of producing the most efficient and economical library service to users.

The goal can be achieved only if we can reduce to a practical minimum the number of technical activities repeated in library after library, with great expense to each. The Council believes that the best way to accomplish this is through national library services—provision of those functions which can be performed on a national basis by a designated agency, whether governmental or private, and shared with other libraries. Cataloging is the first activity that should be considered, for it is basic to library operations. It is also perhaps the most costly and time-consuming. In library terms, cataloging is the dual process of uniquely identifying each publication (descriptive cataloging), and categorizing it by contents (subject analysis). It makes possible the creation of a "record" for each publication, resulting in the bibliographic control that provides the librarian with an inventory of the collection and the user with an essential tool in locating the information he seeks.

In 1974-75, many of the individual pieces of the national library puzzle began to fit together. The Council has attempted to do its share in bringing this about through grants to others, through development of in-house programs to meet specific needs, and through consultation and advice when they have been requested.

Eleven grants totaling \$1,525,538 were made by the Council in this broad category in 1974-75, representing nearly a third of the new

grants made and about half of its new dollar commitment. Three hold-over programs remained active, and eight others were completed.

National Bibliographic Control

A year ago at a three-day meeting jointly sponsored by the Council and the National Science Foundation (NSF), national bibliographic control was defined as "those principles and processes by which bibliographic items [recorded information in various media] are identified to the basic level required for management of and intellectual access to information of all types." It was the further consensus of the participants—forty-five leaders from the fields of librarianship, abstracting and indexing, publishing, information dissemination, and standardization—that a national bibliographic system is needed and will be built, but gradually and at least in part from "programs of action which come out of this meeting."¹

In February 1975, CLR and NSF, joined by the National Commission on Libraries and Information Science (NCLIS), announced the establishment of an Advisory Group on National Bibliographic Control. Its mission: to advise the three sponsoring agencies on how best to coordinate their programs and to recommend priorities for action in this important area. Implementation of the Advisory Group's decisions is handled by Council staff members in the Council's offices.² Now in existence and moving forward are Working Parties on Formats for Journal Articles and Technical Reports, on Bibliographic Name Authority Files, and for a Standard Format for Reporting Serials Holdings. This last is actually Subcommittee 40 of Standards Committee Z-39 of the American National Standards Institute.

Conversion of Serials (CONSER)

Another important step in achieving bibliographic control is the CLR-managed CONSER Project, now in its second year and one of the most widely discussed programs in the library world today.³ The Council has allocated more than a quarter of a million dollars and two full-time professional staff members to managing and coordinating this effort to build a composite national data base of serials. In December 1974, a contract was signed with the Ohio College Library Center (OCLC) for use of its computer facilities.⁴ This major event was followed by agreements with the Library of Congress, the National Library of Canada, and the University of Minnesota to make their serials files available as the initial data base.

The authenticated file produced by CONSER will be available to the library community through the distribution services of the Library of Congress and the National Library of Canada, two of the institutions contributing their serials records on line to the cooperative base. Other

¹ XVIII: 13-14. Citations in this form refer to the Council's annual reports: for example to the *Eighteenth Annual Report*, pages 13-14, in the first instance.

² "CLR, NSF, NCLIS Establish Advisory Group on National Bibliographic Control," *CLR Recent Developments* 3 (May 1975).

³ XVII: 14-15.

⁴ "OCLC, MULS, NFAIS, Aid CONSER Project," *CLR Recent Developments* 3 (May 1975).

participants in the CONSER Project are the National Library of Medicine, National Agricultural Library, Boston Theological Institute, Cornell University for FAUL (Five Associated University Libraries), Florida Union List of Serials Project, New York State Library, State University of New York, University of California, University of Minnesota, and Yale University.⁵

CONSER has been further strengthened by a CLR matching grant with the National Endowment for the Humanities to the National Serials Data Program at the Library of Congress, for the purpose of hastening the completion of the serials data base in the humanities. The National Science Foundation is also assisting with a grant for serials in science and technology.⁶

It had originally been expected that the CONSER Project would be completed by late 1976. However, because of delays in entering the initial files into the OCLC system, it now appears that the goals of the project will not be entirely accomplished before 1977.

Library of Congress

The Library of Congress (LC), a recipient of many Council grants over the years, is a key institution through which CLR cooperates in activities leading toward bibliographic control. This year the Council allocated another quarter of a million dollars (including the NEH grant cited above) for new Library of Congress projects in this area.⁷ Three activities now going forward at the Library of Congress will do much to achieve the desired goal:

1. *Certification of Converted LC Records.* Because the scope of LC's MARC (Machine-Readable Cataloging) coverage for book-form material is still limited, a number of libraries throughout the country are creating their own machine-readable records, basing many of them on LC cataloging copy derived from cards, proof sheets, and entries in the National Union Catalog. The Council grant will enable the Library to accept from authorized participants these locally generated records in machine-readable form, remove the duplicates, compare the records with the official catalog, update them for consistency when required, and redistribute them through the MARC Distribution Service. Participants in the COMARC (Cooperative MARC) project are selected on the basis of the completeness of the data content of their records and their adherence to MARC encoding. They will receive the certified records at no cost during the period of the project; other libraries will be able to purchase the records at nominal cost through the MARC Distribution Service. The project should go far in providing consistency and a degree of standardization to locally created records, thus making their use by others more feasible.

2. *Requirements Study.* The Library of Congress has for some time been involved with the design and implementation of a core biblio-

⁵ Ibid.

⁶ "CLR, NEH Provide Equal Shares in \$237,200 Grant to Library of Congress for CONSER-Related Project," *CLR Recent Developments* 3 (October 1975).

⁷ XVIII: 15; XVI: 12; XV: 20-22.

graphic system, which takes into account the services needed by outside libraries as well as the technical processing requirements for the Library itself. The CLR grant funds a consultant who, together with LC staff, will define the hardware and communications requirements for the system.

3. *National Union Catalog Reporting Format.* Since the initiation of the MARC Distribution Service, there have been discussions concerning the possibility of determining and identifying the minimal number of MARC data elements required to provide unique identification of individual publications. Several studies have been conducted and the conclusions have always been the same: for the purpose of distributing and exchanging machine-readable cataloging records which are to satisfy a multitude of users and uses, no such subset of data from the current LC MARC data can be defined. However, for the specific purpose of reporting titles in machine-readable form to the National Union Catalog, it would be possible to define a less complete record than the present MARC record. This would make the information on holdings available to users in a more timely fashion than at present. The Council grant will make this possible.

Standardization

Webster defines the word *standard* as "something established by authority, custom, or general consent as a model, example, or criterion; something set up or established by authority as a rule for the measure of quantity, weight, extent, value, or quality."⁸ In the context of the Council's work in national and international bibliographic control, standardization means the development and adoption of codes, definitions, rules, and procedures, which will permit a common understanding of the format, control elements, and intellectual content of bibliographic records. If it is to be possible for libraries to exchange information about their holdings, or to share the task of constructing data bases, or to work together in consortia and networks, there must be absolute agreements on the conventions that govern library processes. This becomes even more essential when international exchange of information is involved, and an absolute requirement where automation is a factor.

The American National Standards Institute (ANSI) is responsible for setting voluntary national standards in many fields. Its Committee Z-39, which is directly responsible for standards in library work, documentation, and related publishing practices, has since 1966 received its support from the Council and the National Science Foundation;⁹ this year a new CLR grant of \$14,000 was authorized for the purpose. ANSI is the U. S. member of the International Standards Organization (ISO), which works internationally in much the same way that ANSI does nationally. As the ANSI representative in ISO, Committee Z-39 is in a good position to have U. S. information-handling standards considered for adoption by the international group. CLR staff members participate in several standards working groups, nationally and internationally.

⁸ Webster's Seventh New Collegiate Dictionary (Merriam, 1967).

⁹ XVIII: 15; XVII: 12; XV: 21-22.

Anglo-American Cataloging Rules

The Anglo-American Cataloging Rules (AACR), published in 1967, is a basic tool of catalogers as well as an important force for standardization. It has added immensely to the accessibility of the information in library collections in the English-speaking world and elsewhere. This year CLR made a grant to the American Library Association (ALA) in behalf of the Joint Steering Committee for the Revision of AACR: representatives of ALA, the Canadian Committee on Cataloguing, the [British] Library Association, the British Library, and the Library of Congress. In the seven years that have passed since AACR's publication, certain developments have mandated revision, if this code is to assist libraries attempting to respond to changes in the modern world. Among these developments are the urgent need for reconciliation of differences in the North American and British editions, the number of international standards recently developed, and the cataloging problems presented by relatively new kinds of materials now entering the collections, e.g., audiovisual materials. It is anticipated that the work required for the revision will take two years, with publication to follow shortly thereafter.

Ohio College Library Center

The Ohio College Library Center (OCLC), which became an operating system for Ohio libraries in the early 1970s, today serves over five hundred libraries in thirty-five states. A Council grant to OCLC in May (the fourth since 1970)¹⁰ will assist it in the design and development of acquisitions and authority file subsystems and in contracting for the use of Battelle Memorial Institute's successful free text search system, called BASIS.¹¹

With the acquisitions subsystem, member libraries will be able to search on-line to determine whether wanted items are already on hand or on order. The subsystem will then, if appropriate, automatically prepare order forms, process invoices, issue claims for orders not received, and account for funds. It will also provide fiscal and statistical reports for management.

It is expected that the authority file system will, when developed, record the authoritative form of names together with cross-references to other versions. The names in the authority file will be linked to the bibliographic records in which those names appear. Also scheduled are studies of the utility of authority files in on-line systems from various points of view and of the relative costs of various approaches to their design.

If Battelle's BASIS system can be integrated into the OCLC system, it will permit free text searching on words in bibliographic records in varying combinations of search terms. This addition to its existing capabilities will allow OCLC to offer its member libraries a more than ample combination of search methods.

¹⁰ XVIII: 18-19; XVII: 16-17; XVI: 18.

¹¹ "CLR Supports ASIS's New Indexing Project," *CLR Recent Developments* 3 (July 1975).

Western Interstate Bibliographic Network

The Council has made a grant to the Western Interstate Commission for Higher Education (WICHE) for the design and development of a 17-state (plus British Columbia) Western Interstate Bibliographic Network.¹² The CLR funds will enable a small staff to work full time for a year on the overall design of a system which is intended to be compatible with other developing systems, as well as with the evolving national system. During the course of the grant, the WICHE staff group will develop specifications for the administrative and technical aspects of the Network, and determine its detailed operating cost. They will also provide information about the Network's services, products, and cost to potential members and procure from each of them a letter of intention to participate.

The Council's grant was made in the belief that the development of a variety of regional networks, separate but compatible, is important at this stage of the evolution of a national library program.

Southeastern Library Network

Another regional network is the Southeastern Library Network (SOLINET), now in its second year.¹³ It has to its credit \$280,000 in first year membership fees, a \$600,000 grant from the Mellon Foundation, a cooperative agreement with the well-established and viable Southern Regional Education Board for certain aspects of administration, and a \$10,000 CLR grant toward a training program for librarians participating in the Network. SOLINET member libraries are now receiving services from OCLC. However, with proper management and careful planning, SOLINET has the potential to become a significant regional node in the national bibliographic network of the future.

Stanford University—BALLOTS

A new Council grant to Stanford University is enabling BALLOTS (Bibliographic Automation of Large Library Operations Using a Time-Sharing System) to undertake required development tasks toward completion of a reliable, flexible, and comprehensive on-line network to support and improve services in the Stanford University Libraries and, by extension, in other California libraries.¹⁴ The WICHE Western Bibliographic Network discussed above is also considering the possibility of tying in with BALLOTS and other systems, as it moves ahead with its plans.

Under terms of the new thirty-month grant, BALLOTS staff will alter the software and file structure to support the complete MARC character set, broaden the tape communication system, and expand the comprehensive on-line technical processing services in the Stanford

¹² Ibid.

¹³ XVIII: 19.

¹⁴ "Chicago, Stanford Systems Receive New CLR Grants toward Further Development," *CLR Recent Developments* 3 (May 1975).

libraries, using the University's central computer—an IBM 360/67. At the heart of the system is a 400,000-record file which is accessible through a powerful set of indexes. Currently these indexes provide access to a file of Library of Congress MARC data, a file of individual items being acquired and cataloged by Stanford, and an on-line catalog of the entire collection of the undergraduate library.

For the acquisitions department, BALLOTS currently supports the ordering, claiming, canceling, receiving, and in-process control of monograph materials arriving on regular or standing orders; the receiving and in-process control of materials received on approval or blanket order plans, by exchange, or as gifts; and the ordering, claiming, and canceling of serials.

For the catalog department, the system supports the in-process control, cataloging, and records maintenance of all materials cataloged in the Roman alphabet or normally transliterated.

Southwestern Library Interstate Cooperative Endeavor

The Council's portion of the financial support of the Southwestern Library Interstate Cooperative Endeavor (SLICE) came to an end in December 1974. In the final two quarters of this phase of the two-year grant (CLR's second to the organization), SLICE continued working on various multistate networking proposals involving its six member states (Louisiana, Texas, Arkansas, Oklahoma, New Mexico, and Arizona). In addition to a study of the legal aspects of establishing a Southwestern regional interstate library network, several valuable working papers were developed on such subjects as telecommunications in library networks, computer-based data processing, and models for library network planning.¹⁵ Together with the CLR grants, SLICE has utilized funds from the state library agencies and the U. S. Office of Education to encourage the increased sharing of library resources, services, and expertise within the region.¹⁶ SLICE should continue to play an important role in the development of interstate cooperation.

University of Chicago

A new Council grant this year to the University of Chicago is for the purpose of enabling the University's comprehensive library data management system to achieve full operational status in 1976 and to be available for sharing with other libraries.¹⁷ When completed, the Chicago system is expected to perform a full range of administrative and reader services via the library's Varian minicomputer, which will have direct access to the single integrated data file stored in the University's central computer—an IBM 370/168.

¹⁵ Aronofsky, Julius S. and Karfhage, Robert R., "Telecommunication in Library Networks;" Corbin, John, "Introduction to Computer-Based Data Processing . . .;" and Scholz, William H., "Models for Library Network Planning," (Dallas: Southwestern Library Association, 1975).

¹⁶ XVIII: 20; XVII: 19; XVI: 22.

¹⁷ "Chicago, Stanford Systems Receive New CLR Grants toward Further Development," *CLR Recent Developments* 3 (May 1975).

The CLR grant to the University will be spread out over a seventeen-month period, during which time it is expected that the system will be fully incorporated into the library structure and budget. Until such incorporation occurs, other systems and efforts must be maintained in the library and the costs of dual systems and staffing must be borne.

Bibliographic records in the Chicago system are to be fully compatible with Library of Congress MARC records and hence adaptable for use in other systems, including those supported by CLR. It is hoped that the Chicago system will prove transferable for use by other large libraries or by groups of libraries connected to a central facility via remote terminals.

Bucknell Automated Retrieval and Display System

The Council's 1973 grant to Bucknell University drew to a close this year after meeting some, but not all, of its objectives. A leader in making access to the computer available to all students and faculty at remote terminals, the Bucknell On-line Retrieval and Display System (BARDS) project hoped to extend this access so that users could search the library's bibliographic files.¹⁸ However, unforeseen problems of limited disc space restricted the bibliographic data base to approximately 45,000 out of the projected 200,000 titles. More successful was the expansion of the basic software to include seven ways of accessing information in the data base: author, title, author and title, Library of Congress card number, International Standard Book Number, call number, or borrower. The development of a powerful subject search capability utilizing key terms might well act as a model for similar projects in small to moderate-sized institutions. At the project's close in January 1975, the BARDS system was available to 60 percent of the undergraduate population at Bucknell from any of the forty terminals located on the campus.

American Library Laws

In 1962, the Council awarded \$10,500 to the American Library Association to make possible the publication of the third edition of *American Library Laws*.¹⁹ Terms of the grant specified that revenues derived from sales be used for supplements and new editions. A fourth edition, covering state and federal laws pertaining to libraries as of December 31, 1972, appeared in 1973; the first supplement to that edition, containing laws added, amended, or repealed between January 1, 1973 and December 31, 1974, is now available.

The following is a list of grants approved in the area of automation and national library services during fiscal 1975:

Advisory Group on National Bibliographic Control , for administrative purposes.	\$ 22,000
American Library Association , on behalf of the Joint Steering Committee for Revision of the <i>Anglo-American Cataloging Rules</i> .	111,431

¹⁸ XVII: 18.

¹⁹ XVIII: 16; XII: 21-22; IX: 38; VII: 31.

Boston Theological Institute , to assist with an effort to encourage publishers to imprint the International Standard Serial Number on the cover of serials in religion and theology.	1,000
Conversion of Serials Project (CONSER) , for its development.	250,000
Library of Congress , for the expansion of bibliographic services now provided to the nation's libraries through automated means.	106,132
Library of Congress , with an NEH matching grant, toward creation of a national serials data base in the humanities in machine-readable form.	118,600
Ohio College Library Center , for further system development.	124,250
Stanford University , for further support for BALLOTS.	348,800
University of Chicago , for final development and testing of the Library Data Management System.	350,000
University of North Carolina , for ANSI Committee Z-39.	14,000
Western Interstate Commission for Higher Education , for development of the Western Interstate Bibliographic Network.	79,325
	<hr/> \$1,525,538

professional development

The quality of library programs and services is in direct correlation to the quality of the librarians who administer them. For this reason, the Council has worked increasingly with library leaders in developing opportunities for young and mid-career librarians to improve their skills in their chosen field. The oldest CLR-supported professional development program now in existence is the Fellowship Program which began in 1968. Then, a year and a half ago, the Council announced its Academic Library Management Intern Program, as well as a formal master's degree program at the Graduate Library School of the University of Chicago for individuals who have earned doctorates in other fields and are seriously interested in devoting their talents to library work. And in April of this year, the Council approved an Advanced Study Program for Librarians, designed to further the development of subject specialists for the nation's research and academic libraries.

The selection procedures and standards in all of these programs are rigorous. Applications undergo a preliminary review by distinguished librarians, with the CLR Fellowship Committee taking their recommendations into careful consideration in making the final choices. In the case of the interns and advanced study award recipients, the Selection Committee members interview the leading candidates before making their final decisions.

Advanced Study Program

The new Advanced Study Program will enable up to five qualified librarians with a demonstrated commitment to a specific area of study

to pursue a year of full-time graduate course work in a scholarly discipline—one traditionally considered to be within the “liberal arts and sciences”—at a graduate school of distinction in the chosen field of study.²⁰ The program is not intended to support work in professional areas such as library science, law, business administration, computer science, or management, nor may the funds be used for travel or for writing a dissertation. The awards cover formal graduate study for one academic year (1976-77), with successful candidates receiving stipends of up to \$15,000—based on salary and normal benefits received from the home institution for a comparable period during 1975-76—plus graduate tuition fees for two semesters or three quarters and some assistance for necessary moving costs.

University of Chicago Library Program for Ph.D.'s

This program, like the Advanced Study Program, was instituted in order to attempt to meet a need that had frequently been called to our attention by directors of large research libraries—a need for competent and highly qualified subject specialists to work with scholars and other students.²¹ It is still too soon to measure the success of the University of Chicago program, which is aimed at assisting a limited number of Ph.D. holders in nonlibrary fields to earn an M.A. in library science. That will have to await a report on the postgraduate employment history of the nine students—six in 1974-75 and three in 1975-76—who will have been trained under the program. Any such evaluation will, of course, have to take into consideration the state of the job market for librarians during the period in question.

Academic Library Management Intern Program

The Council's Academic Library Management Intern Program, now nearing completion of its first year, holds great promise of contributing to the development of some of the talented professionals who will manage the nation's great libraries in the future. By working closely with the director and top staff of one of the nation's leading academic libraries, each intern receives a firsthand exposure to situations that will help suggest the skills and techniques required by a leadership job in an academic library.²²

The internship experience is well described in the final report made to the Council by Ralph M. Edwards, who was assistant director of Western Michigan University's School of Librarianship before beginning his intern year. He writes, in part: “When I arrived at the University of Michigan Library last September, my conceptions of what I would be doing and how it would be of specific value to me were quite vague. What I felt I needed most was a chance to put theory into practice,

²⁰ “Council Offers Advanced Study in Academic Discipline to Five Librarians in 1976-77,” *CLR Recent Developments* 3 (July 1975).

²¹ XVIII: 47-48.

²² *Ibid.*

and I imagined the internship as an opportunity to practice management with close and expert guidance. . . . An internship implied to me the *practice* of that which was being learned. . . . It took me some time to realize and to accept the fact that this traditional conception of an internship is inappropriate to management. . . .

"But what I did come to realize after some conceptual adjustments was that the position in which I found myself offered opportunities for types of learning activity different from what I had been expecting and that these activities were ones that I could not have experienced nearly as effectively, if at all, in any practicing management position."

For the second round of awards, more than 300 requests for 1975-76 management intern applications were received at the CLR offices, and over 50 librarians completed the application procedure. Selected from the 12 finalists following personal interviews were:

Linda Beaupré, coordinator of public services at the undergraduate library of the University of California at Berkeley, who will intern with Richard De Gennaro of the University of Pennsylvania;

Jean W. Boyer, chief of collection development at Temple University, assigned to Page Ackerman of the University of California at Los Angeles;

George C. Grant, associate director of public services at the Southern Illinois University (Edwardsville) Library, who will work with Rutherford B. Rogers of Yale University;

Robert Koester, assistant professor and head of the undergraduate reference library at the University of Tennessee, who will intern with Columbia University's Warren J. Haas; and

Lee Ann Putnam, associate librarian at Gallaudet College, assigned to Virginia P. Whitney of Rutgers University.

CLR Fellowship Program

The Council's formal support of professional development for librarians began in a modest manner in 1968 with a fellowship program for librarians. Including those librarians selected for CLR Fellowships in 1975-76, 165 awards (totaling a little more than half a million dollars) have been announced in the past seven years.²³ Events have served to justify many of the Council's choices; a surprisingly large number of fellows have moved on to more important library posts, the latest of these being the newly appointed university librarian at Princeton and the new director of libraries at MIT.

The twenty-six 1975-76 recipients will devote 'from three to nine months to self-developed study and research projects in areas ranging from computer-based reference service in academic libraries to the administration of rare book and special collections departments in large public university libraries. As in previous years, CLR Fellows will re-

²³ XVIII: 49-51; XVII: 49-51; XVI: 46-48; XV: 17-19; XIV: 44-46; XIII: 41-42; XII: 35.

ceive funds for approved travel, supplies, and services from the Council, and an appropriate leave of absence from their employers to carry out their projects.

Recipients of Council on Library Resources fellowships for the academic year 1975-76 and their projects are as follows:

Judith Armstrong, director of the library, Drury College (Mo.). To survey attitudes, employment practices, and the progress of affirmative action programs for women in libraries.

Pauline Atherton, professor, School of Information Studies, Syracuse University. To survey the real and potential impact of computer-based reference service in academic libraries.

Martha J. Bailey, physics librarian, Purdue University. To study the position of the middle manager in the academic library organization.

Boyd M. Bolvin, associate dean of instruction, Bellevue Community College (Wash.). To examine external degree programs in higher education in the U. S.

Keith M. Cottam, assistant director for the Undergraduate Library, University of Tennessee at Knoxville. To study the issues involved in the utilization of specialists in large academic libraries, with emphasis on technical specialists.

Doris C. Dale, associate professor, Department of Instructional Materials, Southern Illinois University at Carbondale. To gather data and information about community college libraries for a book on current trends and practices and to enrich her background for courses taught in this area.

Lynn C. Dennison, professional assistant, Association of College and Research Libraries, American Library Association, Chicago. To gather information on organizational patterns in library and media services in community and junior colleges and to evaluate these patterns in terms of their usefulness in meeting information needs of users.

Barbara L. Feret, director of the library, Culinary Institute of America, Hyde Park, New York. To survey, identify, and analyze strengths of important historically oriented collections on gastronomy and cookery.

Thelma Freides, associate professor, School of Library Service, Atlanta University. To prepare a bibliographic guide to the reports which officials of the federal government are required to submit to Congress.

Wolfgang M. Freitag, fine arts librarian, Harvard College Library, Harvard University. To complete work on and prepare for publication a section for "Sources of Information in the Humanities."

Jane C. Henning, head, Howe Architecture Library, Arizona State University at Tempe. To study libraries associated with schools of architecture in the United States.

Judith Holliday, librarian, Fine Arts Library, Cornell University. To complete a holdings list of 19th century American architectural periodicals.

Richard G. Landon, assistant head, Thomas Fisher Rare Book Library, University of Toronto. To study the administration of rare book and special collections departments in large public university libraries.

Alan H. MacDonald, health science librarian, Dalhousie University (Halifax, N.S.). To study the various organizational models which universities have adopted to accommodate the "special" circumstances of professional school libraries.

James W. McGregor, head of the library's technical services, Northeastern Illinois University. To study staffing for serials processing in large university libraries.

Joan K. Marshall, chief of the library's Catalog Division, Brooklyn College. To construct a thesaurus of nonsexist subject headings.

Ann F. Painter, professor, Graduate School of Library Science, Drexel University. To determine the functions of traditional library classifications in research libraries in the United States.

James F. Parks, Jr., head librarian, Millsaps College (Miss.). To carry out an internship at the Georgia Institute of Technology.

Stephen L. Peterson, librarian, Divinity School, Yale University. To do basic research for a bibliographic guide to Protestant missions.

Eugene E. Petriwsky, assistant director for technical services, University of Colorado Library. To study the effect of proposed changes in the 8th edition of the *Library of Congress List of Subject Headings* on medium-sized academic libraries.

Hannelore B. Rader, orientation librarian, Eastern Michigan University. To study 10 successful library instruction programs in academic libraries and summarize findings in the form of a guide.

Donald L. Roberts, audiovisual librarian, Hennepin County Library (Edina, Minn.). To examine past and present censorship of nonbook media in public libraries.

Earl R. Schwass, library director, Naval War College (Newport, R.I.). To study user education programs of senior military and graduate school libraries with particular reference to the needs of midcareer military officers.

Patricia H. Shoyinka, cataloger, Ibadan University Library, Ibadan, Nigeria. To study the use of MARC records for catalog production in selected North American libraries in order to determine basic criteria for the use of MARC records in Nigeria.

Mildred C. Tietjen, director of library services, Georgia Southwestern College. To compare and evaluate instructional programs at ALA-accredited graduate library schools.

Joyce L. White, librarian, Penniman Library of Education, University of Pennsylvania. To organize available information on church libraries in order to produce a reference tool on church libraries.

The following is a list of grants approved in fiscal 1975 for professional development programs:

Academic Library Management Intern Program , to continue for two more years a CLR program to give on-the-job training each year to up to five potential directors of the nation's leading academic and research libraries.	\$265,000
Advanced Study Program , to assist up to five well-qualified librarians who desire advanced formal academic training in a scholarly discipline.	115,000
CLR Fellowship Program , to provide support for the CLR Fellows selected for 1975-76.	72,823
	<hr/> \$452,823

management

Almost without exception the programs discussed in this annual report were developed and funded because they met the requirements of two standards the Council has followed in determining its direction and in selecting projects for support: Does the work show promise of providing a solution to a significant library problem? Will it enable libraries to use their funds economically and efficiently and thus serve scholars and other users more effectively? This latter point becomes increasingly important in the present economic situation, when inflation and rising personnel costs each year take a larger bite out of the library's budget. Several university librarians have reported that in the last few years they have had to reduce their expenditures for books and periodicals by about 30 percent. Others are in the same plight. If this situation is not reversed, irretrievable damage will be done to the collections and consequently to scholarship and the advancement of knowledge.

While the activities described in the previous sections have a strong relationship to the effective use of funds, other responsibilities facing the directors of large academic and research libraries on a day-to-day basis require a different kind of approach, a broad program that attempts to assist them in dealing with the management problems that arise in library after library.

As early as 1968 the Council embarked on discussions centering on how best to help academic libraries redirect their management procedures into proven efficient methods.²⁴ Because the techniques of good administration developed for business and government cannot be applied unaltered to a service-oriented institution like the library, during the early stages of the overall program the Council worked with top-flight management specialists to help them gain an understanding of the nature of libraries and their needs.

²⁴ XIII: 24.

Recognizing that the success of the program depended on having at least the acquiescence of the universities of which academic libraries are a part, the Council from the beginning involved top academic administrators intimately in the planning process. The first significant grant was to the Association of Research Libraries (ARL) for a preliminary study by Booz, Allen & Hamilton of management practices in large university libraries.²⁵ An advisory committee of university librarians and presidents worked with the study team every step of the way in what proved to be a remarkably effective partnership, and the resultant report provided a useful foundation for further efforts to improve management practices.

The study also led to the establishment within ARL of the effective Office of University Library Management Studies, now in its fifth year and supported chiefly by Council funds.²⁶ The office director (a librarian) received his on-the-job management training as a full-time member of the Booz, Allen team that carried out the next phase of the overall program: the CLR-funded study of the organization and staffing of the Columbia University Libraries, which took place in 1971-1972.

Office of University Library Management Studies

Scheduled to complete its fifth year in the fall, ARL's Office of University Library Management Studies (OMS) has provided assistance to virtually all of its constituency, as well as to nonmembers of ARL, with its practical research and development, organizational training programs, and information exchange. These activities will be continued with the support of a new three-year CLR grant.

One of the Office's most significant contributions has been the Management Review and Analysis Program (MRAP), a carefully structured design for library management self-studies. The studies have had an important impact well beyond the libraries themselves. In attempting to respond to some of the questions raised in the study process, the parent institutions have frequently found it necessary to review their own goals, plans, patterns, and procedures and to take another—generally more realistic—look at the library as a component of the total academic community. In view of the stepchild role so often assigned to the library, top-level administrative assessment of its place and purpose cannot fail to be helpful. Twenty-one research libraries have participated in MRAP to date, and this intensive evaluation of management practices will be undertaken by other libraries in the years ahead.

New programs under consideration by OMS and its advisory group, the ARL Management Commission, are: (1) study of the public services function in research libraries, (2) design of a performance audit technique, and (3) development of specialized training packages for application in research libraries.

From the time the first CLR grant for the Office was made, ARL itself has always made some contribution to its expenses. This has

²⁵ Ibid.

²⁶ XVIII: 23-24; XVII: 24-25; XVI: 11.

gradually been increased with each succeeding year, and during the last year of the new grant, well over half the cost of operating the Office will be met by the ARL contribution and by receipts from the sale of OMS publications and services.

In the area of management, as with national library services and automation, the Council is of the opinion that there is more than one way to approach a goal. Thus, in addition to the support given to early management studies of university libraries and the creation of the ARL Office of University Library Management Studies, the Council has provided funds for projects that attempt to solve the problems through other means. Two such approaches are described below, one a research and development unit within a library, the other a library planning office. Their example should be of service to other institutions seeking ways to help the library make an effective contribution to the learning process.

Joint University Libraries

The CLR-sponsored research and development unit of the Joint University Libraries (JUL) of Nashville, Tennessee, now in its sixth year, continues to be helpful to JUL and its constituent libraries (Vanderbilt University, Peabody and Scarritt colleges).²⁷ In-house activities this year have ranged from professional evaluation and affirmative action to statistical studies of library users from institutions other than JUL members.

Columbia University

Columbia University's Library Planning Office has just completed its third and last year of CLR support.²⁸ The Office continues to work closely with the various divisions of the library in order to extend library and information service planning capabilities at the University. In the course of this year much important work has been undertaken, including analysis of the Rare Book and Manuscript Library, the East Asian Library, and the Law Library. A financial analysis task force has been created to identify major functional applications of funds within the libraries, recommend areas of potential cost reduction, identify constraints in effecting change and recommend means to overcome them, and identify opportunities for funding to aid in the process of change. The task force will disseminate its findings to the staff as a means of stimulating staff contributions to improve cost effectiveness. The University is committed to continue support of the Planning Office as a permanent unit of the library structure.

Moderate-sized Academic Libraries

In keeping with its charter, the Council's major concern continues to be the large academic/research library. But, with inflation of both dollars and documents creating management problems in the libraries of hun-

²⁷ XVIII: 24-25; XVII: 25; XVI: 11-12.

²⁸ XVIII: 24-25; XVII: 25; XVI: 10-11.

dreds of smaller institutions of higher learning as well, a new project has been added – this one aimed at the broad development of the mid-sized and smaller academic library. As a first step, the Council has made a grant to the University of North Carolina at Charlotte for a project to design and test an academic library development program. A major product is expected to be a library self-study manual for possible use by the nation’s small to moderate-sized academic libraries. A self-study of this sort should be helpful as those libraries review their goals, functions, and practices with the purpose of increasing library effectiveness and improving the allocation and use of available resources. Drawing on the MRAP experience and with the OMS director available as a consultant, principles of sound practice, tailored to meet the specific needs of this group of institutions, will be developed to aid in assessing the budget processes and financial support provided the library; internal library planning and control routine; and the organizational, supervisory, personnel, and service practices of the library.

The following is a list of grants approved in the area of management during fiscal 1975:

Academic Library Development Program (Council-administered), for projects that will assist in the development and management of small to medium-sized academic libraries. Of this amount, \$47,046 was allocated to the University of North Carolina at Charlotte for the design and testing of an academic library development program.	\$100,000
Association of Research Libraries , for continuation of the Office of University Library Management Studies (OMS).	210,000
	<u>\$310,000</u>

preservation and microforms

Preservation of library materials has always been a problem for libraries, but for tomorrow’s custodians of books and periodicals the problem will be even greater, as more and more materials are added to the collections. It has been demonstrated that the paper in many of the newer books and periodicals is more prone to deterioration than is that in other publications hundreds of years old. Council-supported research some years ago determined that acidity in paper was the primary factor in its deterioration; as papermaking technology has evolved over the centuries, the resultant product has become increasingly acid and has

otherwise been progressively weakened by the chemistry and mechanics of the processes involved. In the continuing struggle against deterioration of library materials, the Council has provided support for the William J. Barrow Research Laboratory in Richmond, Va., the Preservation Research and Testing Office of the Library of Congress, and the New England Document Conservation Office. A new grant this year to the Barrow Laboratory has enabled it to continue its research activities, principally in the deacidification of books. The Library of Congress Office and the New England Document Conservation Center are now self-supporting, with funds received from their parent organizations and/or sale of services. A smaller grant in this area for a research project involving paper restoration, conducted in Italy by Margaret Hey, has drawn to a close.

Not all deteriorating books and journals, however, can benefit from deacidification. Many are already in such weakened condition that their physical preservation is not feasible. For these the most effective approach is preservation of the information they contain, and microfilming is the most effective way of accomplishing that end. Its costs are much less than those of conventional reprinting or of any other practical method of restoring the original publications or recording their contents.

Microfilm offers other important benefits to libraries. It provides a means of greatly reducing the storage requirements for bulky and voluminous materials such as newspapers; it also affords a relatively inexpensive means of reproducing and disseminating materials for which the demand is small or unpredictable.

In the most recently published *Academic Library Statistics* (1973-74) of the Association of Research Libraries, it is noted that the median collection of total microform units held by its 82 university library members jumped from 290,944 to 733,755 in the six-year period between 1967-68 and 1973-74.²⁹ As for preservation microfilming, in fiscal 1974 alone the Library of Congress reported that over 5,700,000 negative microfilm exposures had been made to preserve books, periodicals, and newspapers in the Library's collections; the number of materials thus treated has increased annually since the program's inception in the late 1960s.³⁰

CLR has been active from its beginning in supporting, coordinating, and encouraging the utilization of microfilm and other micrographic techniques. In its early years a good deal of emphasis was placed on hardware development. More recently, the Council's focus has shifted to library applications of micrographics and other activities that provide librarians and their suppliers with practical information about microfilms and their effective use in the library. Two significant CLR-supported projects of this nature are nearing completion: the formulation of a national standard for the advertising of micropublications³¹ and the

²⁹ Association of Research Libraries, *Academic Library Statistics 1973-74* (Washington: Association of Research Libraries, 1974).

³⁰ *Annual Report of the Librarian of Congress for the Fiscal Year Ending June 30, 1974* (Washington: Government Printing Office, 1975).

³¹ "New Advertising Standard Approved," *CLR Recent Developments* 3 (May 1975).

preparation of a manual that will allow persons without technical knowledge to evaluate microfiche reading machines for library usage.³² The manual, now being printed, will be distributed without cost to libraries and similar institutions.

The Council has for a number of years had on its staff a micrographics specialist who acts as a consultant to libraries and library organizations and also serves as a link between them and commercial interests. He is a member of the board of directors of the National Microfilm Association, a consultant to the Micropublishing Project Committee of the American Library Association, and chairman of the American National Standards Institute's subcommittee on the advertising of micropublications.

Barrow Laboratory

Major products of the Council's long-term support of the Barrow Laboratory have been specifications for permanent and durable paper and the Barrow one- and two-bath processes for deacidifying paper. In the last few years the Laboratory has, among other things, revised its specifications for permanent and durable paper, evaluated the lasting qualities of the new papers which appear to be dominating the market, and investigated the effect of temperature and humidity on the useful life of paper. But the most concentrated effort has been in the development of a morpholine vapor deacidification process for books in bulk, now in the last phases of testing.³³ In order to insure that libraries will benefit from this new development at minimum expense, the Council has arranged patenting and licensing through the nonprofit Research Corporation. CLR's royalties from this agreement, if any, would be applied to further preservation research.

Library of Congress Preservation Office

During this year the Library of Congress informed the Council that CLR support was no longer required for the LC Preservation Research Office. The Office was activated in 1971, with the help of a \$94,500 Council grant for the purchase of equipment. In the years since, the Office has performed important services to libraries and others in addition to conducting basic research.³⁴ Its final report to CLR noted that the Preservation Office "is giving high priority to large scale tests of diethylzinc vapor as a vapor phase deacidification agent for books." Also noted was a wide range of activities engaged in by the Office—from evaluation of the life of Xerox paper to identification of indelible ink for stamping books.

New England Document Conservation Center

The New England Document Conservation Center's final report on its two-year grant from the Council indicates that self-supporting status

³² XVII: 35.

³³ XVIII: 35-36.

³⁴ XVIII: 36.

was reached in one and a half years of operation. Estimated income for 1974-75 from non-CLR sources is \$236,750—up from \$77,148 during the first year. In addition to its restoration activities for libraries, archives, and related governmental agencies in the six-state region, the Center has become a clearinghouse for conservation information and the source to which many librarians and others turn for assistance, guidance, and instruction in the care of their materials.³⁵ The Center has in a short time achieved considerable recognition; it is the hope of the Council that the success of this model will encourage other regional groupings of libraries to undertake similar programs.

Archival Paper Restoration Techniques

In December 1971, Margaret Hey, an English chemist, received a Council grant to conduct research into book and archival paper restoration techniques along scientific lines. The experiments were conducted at the Istituto di Patologia del Libro in Rome, Italy.³⁶ Early this year, after the final report of the project was received, Miss Hey informed the Council that she has returned to England to complete work on the chapter concerning her research which will appear in Anthony Cains' Council-supported workshop manual on restoration of printed books and parchment manuscripts.

The following grants were approved in fiscal 1975 for continued work in microforms and preservation research:

W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory, Inc. , toward continued operation of the Laboratory for a two-year period.	\$240,000
Microfiche Reader Testing Project , to develop a device which will enable persons without technical knowledge to evaluate microfiche reading machines for library use; supplement.	4,000
	\$244,000

³⁵ XVIII: 36-37; XVII: 37.

³⁶ XVI: 42.

improving services to users

Libraries exist to serve people. Computers, management techniques, and the like are only the mechanisms that make it possible for libraries to help users meet their educational, cultural, professional, or personal requirements for information and knowledge. Since its inception in 1956, the Council has expended approximately 20 percent of its available program funds on a variety of projects to improve services of libraries to their special clienteles whose requirements must be identified and met. Substantial sums have been invested in projects dealing with such diverse subjects as nontraditional education and the creation of union lists and other library tools.

College Library Program

A most significant program in this area of Council activity is the College Library Program, since 1969 supported jointly with the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) by a \$1,600,000 fund.³⁷

Under the program, grants are made to undergraduate institutions that submit acceptable plans—developed cooperatively by the college administration, faculty, and library staff—intended to enhance the library's role in the education of students in the broad area of the humanities. Each institution must commit itself over the period of the five-year grant to match the CLR-NEH contribution.

Six such grants in 1974-75 brought to twenty-three the number of colleges participating in the program. Four of the original recipients are nearing completion of their five-year programs, and the Council and NEH are presently studying the impact of the individual projects in broadening the library's role on campus. Also nearing completion is a similar program at Wabash College, which does not accept federal funds and therefore receives support from the Council alone. The 1974-75 recipients and their five-year plans follow.

Clark College of Atlanta, Georgia, intends to make it possible for librarians to share their expertise via team teaching. The teams are composed of instructors in its freshman studies program and graduate library assistants from neighboring Atlanta University's School of Library Science. It is anticipated that expanded use of the library by the students will also add to their reading skills.

³⁷ XVIII: 25; XVII: 26-27; XVI: 12; XV: 34-35.

Kearney State College of Nebraska is also aiming its program at freshmen. Through the five-year project the college hopes to provide approximately 1,200 freshman English students each year with the experience of learning the organized general search process necessary for all levels of research. Another important goal is to develop ways in which this search process can be incorporated into the departmental curriculum.

Mills College of California has developed a program to focus attention on and encourage the use of humanities materials in the library, including those in the rare books and manuscripts collection. A project librarian, who also serves as curator of the rare books collection, has been added to the library staff. She has developed bibliographic courses, field trips, and special events intended to help the collection become a basic element in the college's instructional program.

Pacific University of Oregon will build on its library's experience with a tutoring program for disadvantaged students in carrying out a project for all students entitled "Maximum Instructional Effectiveness through Maximum Usage of Library Materials." An English department faculty member, reporting directly to the librarian, works with an instructional aide in diagnosing learning problems among students, matching some of the students with "peer tutors." The faculty member also attempts to acquaint the students with librarians in order to dispel any reluctance they may have to ask for assistance in the library.

University of Kentucky is providing liaison between the library and the General Studies Division of the university under a new library services coordinator. The coordinator teaches certain segments of courses where library experience is needed and is also available for instructing and advising individual students about term papers and research projects.

University of Utah is enlarging its staff to include an orientation coordinator to direct a program with these major goals: (1) creation of a librarian-faculty-student effort to define library-teaching priorities; (2) locating and assisting students who lack library skills; (3) development of flexible programs of library instruction for use in classroom, workshop, tutorial, or self-instruction situations; and (4) program evaluation.

Eastern Michigan's LOEX

Directly related to the CLR-NEH College Library Program is Eastern Michigan University's Library Orientation-Instruction Exchange (LOEX), a clearinghouse for information and materials relating to academic library orientation instruction at almost 200 institutions. Begun in May 1972 as a result of Eastern Michigan's Library Outreach Orientation Program (a recipient of a CLR-NEH College Library Program grant), LOEX is broadening its services under the half-time direction of a member of the University's Center of Educational Resources faculty. Basic LOEX objectives are: (1) to facilitate communication among academic libraries in developing such programs, (2) to assist libraries in

developing such programs, and (3) to aid librarians on an informal basis in their research endeavors and in furthering their education in orientation activities. The university is hopeful that Project LOEX will prove largely self-supporting by the end of the CLR grant and in any event is committed to carrying on the work as a continuing part of its service program.

Book and Periodical Selection

Careful book and periodical selection is vital if academic libraries are to contribute all they are capable of to the educational process. In the early 1960's, the Council supported an Association of College and Research Libraries project intended to assist librarians in this important task. The project resulted in the establishment of *Choice* magazine, a standard selection tool today in most college and university libraries as well as in numerous public and special libraries.³⁸ Published monthly, *Choice* is now in its twelfth year. It has been self-supporting since 1969.

In 1974-75, *Choice* decided to add a department concerned with the evaluation of recently issued periodicals, and sought the cooperation of Evan Ira Farber, Earlham College librarian and author of *Classified List of Periodicals for the College Library* (5th edition published in 1972). The Council has made a small three-year grant to Earlham College toward the expense to the library of Mr. Farber's *Choice* column, entitled "Periodicals for College Libraries."

Core Collection Project

At the close of the fiscal year, publication by the American Library Association of the second edition of *Books for College Libraries* was imminent. With the help of CLR, the first edition was published in 1967.³⁹ The new edition was prepared under the direction of ALA's Association of College and Research Libraries. A computerized list of the 40,000 or so essential titles for a college library, it will serve libraries as a basis for qualitative analysis as well as a guide to selecting publications for their collections. The Council has been active in planning, monitoring, and underwriting the overall project.

Consumers' Handbook for Public Libraries

While the Council's financial investment in the public library sector over the years has not been large, in terms of impact the projects supported have been significant. A small grant to the Public Library Association of ALA is enabling that organization to prepare a "Consumers' Handbook for Public Libraries," a guide to public library services offered to specific groups, such as children, youth, women, students, businessmen, homeowners, blacks, Spanish-speaking, etc. Each of the approximately 21 articles will be written by a prominent individual and followed by a response from an equally prominent librarian. The project's goal is the formulation of a "statement to direct widespread atten-

³⁸ VIII: 20.

³⁹ XIII: 36-37.

tion to the American public library as an active community agent capable of meeting the real needs of real people today and in the future.”

Community Information Role of Public Library

New York City’s well-publicized plan to link the Brooklyn Public Library’s 55 branches to a computerized data bank, thus enabling them to provide available information about public services and programs on a personalized basis, unfortunately never came to fruition.⁴⁰ The Council commitment has therefore been withdrawn. However, the publicity surrounding the CLR commitment when made three years ago may have been helpful to other city libraries which sought and received federal funds for similar projects.

Los Angeles Public Library Study

“A Community Responsive Branch Program: A Study of Community Attitudes for the Los Angeles Library System” (Los Angeles, Deasy, Bolling & Gill, 1975) is the title of a report growing out of a project cooperatively supported by CLR and the Educational Facilities Laboratories.⁴¹ The study was conducted by an architect, a social psychologist, and opinion researchers, who first attempted to determine through a variety of means (observation, interviews with users and library staff, statistics, etc.) the current patterns of library use in four branches with disparate populations. Once this was accomplished, questionnaires and personal interviews with a random sample of both users and nonusers in each of the four areas resulted in recommendations of new, often nontraditional, library services which would better serve the real needs of each community. In order to attract new clients, the report strongly emphasizes the need for branch librarians to promote, indeed to aggressively “market,” available library services.

Library Independent Study Program

Now in its third year, the College Entrance Examination Board’s (CEEB) Office of Library Independent Study and Guidance Projects is continuing its focus on public libraries already offering independent study opportunities to their constituencies.⁴² Eleven libraries have participated in the program: Atlanta, Cleveland, Denver, Enoch Pratt (Baltimore), Miami-Dade, Portland (Maine), Salt Lake City, St. Louis, Tulsa City-County, Worcester, and the Free Public Library of Woodbridge (New Jersey). During this third year of the project, a Learner’s Advisory Service has been introduced at nine libraries, with provision made for data collection and evaluation. Assessment of user and services data from four of these—Atlanta, Tulsa, Portland (Maine), and Salt Lake City—shows that independent study projects have been successful both in establishing a need for such services and in attracting and assisting adults with learning projects. As the nine libraries continue to expand their services, modifications are being made in order to define

⁴⁰ XVIII: 28; XVII: 33; XVI: 27-28.

⁴¹ XVIII: 29; XVII: 32-33.

⁴² XVIII: 28; XVII: 31-32; XVI: 28.

more explicitly an "adult learner" and describe individual learning projects; to obtain more information on staff costs in terms of time spent in preparation, interviews with learners, gathering materials, and making inquiries or referrals; and to determine the effectiveness of nationally prepared versus locally created advertising. The Office is funded by CLR, the National Endowment for the Humanities, and U. S. Office of Education, as well as by the CEEB itself.

Support of Indexes

From time to time, the Council assists in the preparation of a specialized index or guide for librarians and their constituents. In 1974-75, such assistance took the form of nominal aid to Professor Donald M. Jacobs of Northeastern University, Boston, for expenses in preparing photo-ready manuscript of his index to black newspapers published before the Civil War, and a more sizable grant to the American Society for Information Science (ASIS) toward preparation of a 25-year cumulative index of the *Journal of the American Society for Information Science (JASIS)*, to be available in both book and machine-readable form.

The *JASIS* index will approximate a "core collection" of information science periodical literature. It is expected that the project will develop generally accepted indexing terminology and standards which will prove valuable to the profession as a whole. As a condition of the CLR grant, ASIS has agreed that the *JASIS* cumulative index in book and computer tape form will be made available at a moderate price, commensurate with a reasonable recovery of costs and overhead, and that a percentage of any profits from sales will be earmarked for future updates.

Users in Government

Nearing completion, the New York State Library's Council-supported study of state government information needs is engendering considerable interest among state librarians, researchers, and budget analysts.⁴³ According to the June progress report, sixty persons attending a May 2 workshop were so enthusiastic about the findings that they volunteered to form a working committee to foster greater visibility of agency information resources and to improve interlibrary loan procedures between agency libraries and the New York State Library.

The following is a list of grants approved in fiscal 1975 in order to help improve library services:

American Library Association , toward preparation and publication of a consumers' handbook for public libraries.	\$ 8,372
American Society for Information Science , toward a 25-year cumulative index to the <i>Journal of the American Society for Information Science</i> .	19,910
Earlham College , for three-year assistance (excluding personnel expense) in preparing a regular <i>Choice</i> magazine column on periodical selection.	7,500

⁴³ XVIII: 32.

Eastern Michigan University, to support expansion of its Library Orientation-Instruction Exchange (LOEX) over the next three years. 41,969

Donald M. Jacobs, for expenses in preparing photo-ready manuscript of his index to black newspapers published before the Civil War. 500

National Endowment for the Humanities, with an NEH matching grant for further funding of the joint CLR-NEH College Library Program. Projects funded under this program for fiscal 1976: 100,000

Clark College	\$23,000
Kearney State College	23,000
Mills College	24,304
Pacific University	25,000
University of Kentucky	25,000
University of Utah	25,500

In each case, a matching grant has been made to the institution from NEH, and the total grant is matched by the institution itself.

\$178,251

international activities

The Council's commitment to international cooperation among libraries and groups of libraries continues to contribute to the exchange of information among the world's nations and cultures. The Council has long recognized the extreme importance of cooperation in global terms, for the interests of scholarship and the libraries that serve it transcend national boundaries and concerns.

International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA)

When the Council began its work, its grants for international activities were made generally in response to requests which dealt with problems on an almost *ad hoc* basis, as seen by persons with varying viewpoints. However, by the late 1960s it was apparent that to attain satisfactory library development both in the United States and abroad, national and international planning on a more organized basis was necessary. The International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA) seemed the logical organization with which to work, for it was already attempting to provide the needed structure to enable libraries around the world to focus on common problems and work together toward their solutions. The Council has supported this effort with a series of grants, the most

recent of which will help to bring IFLA closer to its goal of becoming self-supporting.⁴⁴

"National and International Planning" became the theme of IFLA's 40th General Council Meeting, held in Washington, D. C. in November 1974 and supported in part with a CLR grant.⁴⁵ At the closing plenary session, Robert Vosper—an IFLA vice president, conference chairman, and CLR board member—repeated British Library director H. T. Hookway's opinion that "national systems can no longer flourish on their own, and it is important to achieve the maximum practical level of international standardization so that records and information can be shared without difficulty."⁴⁶ Nowhere is the necessity for international cooperation and information exchange more critical than in the area of universal bibliographic control, a dream held for generations by many, which relies on the wide acceptance and application of international standards.

Universal Bibliographic Control

"Librarians are internationalists at heart—from the nature of their pre-occupation and the conditions of their profession," wrote Dorothy Anderson, director of the IFLA International Office for Universal Bibliographic Control (UBC).⁴⁷ The accuracy of this statement cannot be held in doubt when one considers the increasing acceptance of and work toward the objective promulgated by the UBC Office—the creation of a single bibliographic record for each item of knowledge published anywhere in the world. This record, to be truly universal, must be in a form readily acceptable in exchange among national libraries and bibliographic centers, a form which makes explicit the necessity for an international standard format. The format itself must be substantial enough to carry sufficient bibliographic information in order to preclude the necessity for recataloging the item in every national, regional, or local center that acquires it. It must be flexible enough to permit the addition or modification of data for local or national purposes if necessary. The record thus formatted and exchanged must be equally capable of use in manual and machine systems. The vision inspired by this objective is of a world-wide system for the control and exchange of bibliographic information.

For several years, the Council has supported IFLA's work in this area, first through the Cataloguing Secretariat, more recently through its successor, the International Office for UBC.⁴⁸ Endorsed and partially supported by UNESCO, the UBC Office spearheads efforts toward its objective by organizing and staffing special-purpose working groups to agree on ways to deal with specific problems, by holding regional work-

⁴⁴ XVIII: 43; XVII: 40-41; XVI: 37-38.

⁴⁵ XVIII: 44-45; XVII: 43.

⁴⁶ Robert Vosper, "Report on the Next Stages of Library Planning, based on the Unesco and IFLA Conferences," *IFLA Journal* 1-2 (1975).

⁴⁷ Dorothy Anderson, "IFLA's Programme for UBC: the Background and the Basis," *IFLA Journal* 1-1 (1975).

⁴⁸ XVIII: 44; XVII: 41-42; XVI: 38.

shops that encourage national library systems (particularly in developing countries) to evolve and grow, by keeping the international library community informed through its publications, and by coordinating as well as originating the many activities that must go forward all over the world if universal bibliographic control is to become a reality.

The UBC Office also has a vital role in the development of the standards without which communication between libraries—locally, nationally, internationally—is impossible. To this end, the UBC Office has carried on an aggressive publication program through the IFLA Committee on Cataloguing. In addition to the quarterly *International Cataloguing*, three new publications involving uniform headings—personal, corporate and legislative—are now available.⁴⁹

In large part because of the energetic efforts of UBC Office personnel, the concept of universal bibliographic control is beginning to be widely supported all over the world. This is especially evident in the grants the office has received from national library organizations in Australia, Canada, Denmark, Federal Republic of Germany, Japan, the U. S., and from UNESCO. The British Library's contribution consists of providing the UBC Office with space, facilities, and services. The UBC Office has taken important steps during its first full year of existence; the Council has extended its support for two additional years through June 30, 1977.

International Council on Archives

Encouraged in some measure by the successes of IFLA, the Council has acted favorably on a request from the International Council on Archives (ICA) for support to strengthen its relatively new secretariat. A three-year grant has been made to ICA to make possible the addition to the secretariat staff of an executive assistant and a bilingual secretary. They will aid the executive director and relieve in part the volunteer archivists whose extensive contributed efforts have been largely responsible for the work of the organization since its establishment in 1950. It is expected that with a strengthened full-time staff, this world organization of the archival profession will be able to expand its programs in such areas as: (1) the development and training of archivists, (2) the microfilming and preservation of materials, and (3) the publishing of guides to sources of the history of nations. In addition to receiving dues support from the world's archives, the ICA Secretariat is housed at no cost in the French National Archives. An expected increase in dues, anticipated royalties from its publications, and additional grants and contracts from international bodies are expected to make the ICA self-supporting at the termination of the CLR grant on June 30, 1978.

⁴⁹ *The Arrangement of Entries for Complex Material under Headings for Personal Authors* (\$4.50); *Corporate Headings: Their Use in Library Catalogues and National Bibliographies: a Comparative and Critical Study*, by Eva Verona (\$13.00); *List of Uniform Headings for Higher Legislative and Ministerial Bodies in European Countries*, compiled by the USSR Cataloguing Committee, 1st ed. (\$12.00). All three published by IFLA Committee on Cataloguing (London: 1975); available in North America from Canadian Library Association, 151 Sparks Street, Ottawa, Ontario K1P 5E3 Canada.

Other International Information Exchanges

While supporting the work of international bodies on an organizational basis is one way of promoting international cooperation, the Council has supported other, more individual efforts as well. From its inception, the Council has encouraged the international exchange of information and learning by helping to send librarians and others whose work is important to libraries to significant conferences and meetings in various parts of the world. In the past year, the Council awarded five travel grants which enabled the recipients to present papers, chair conferences, and represent views of the American library community in England, Accra, and Paris. Another grant enabled a participant from a developing country to attend an international summer school for workers in the information field, supported in part by UNESCO's Division of Scientific and Technological Information and Documentation.

Yet another aspect of this activity is to bring important foreign librarians to visit the United States. Accordingly, Dr. Hans-Peter Geh, Director of the Württembergische Landesbibliothek in Stuttgart, spent the month of August 1974 visiting twelve major U. S. libraries, as well as several library schools and organizations that work with libraries.

From broad international concerns, such as the work toward universal bibliographic control, to increasing international awareness of library methods and programs on a personal level, the trend toward international cooperation and thinking has never been more strongly focused.

The following is a list of grants approved in fiscal 1975 for projects with an international focus:

Hans-Peter Geh , to enable Dr. Geh to engage in a study tour of major U. S. libraries and associated activities.	\$ 3,500
UNESCO , to provide one fellowship for a participant from a developing country to attend an international summer school in information.	2,200
International Council on Archives , for partial support of the ICA Secretariat for a three-year period.	72,000
International Federation of Library Associations , for continued support of the IFLA Secretariat through January 30, 1976.	45,000
International Federation of Library Associations , for continued support of the IFLA Office for Universal Bibliographic Control through July 1977.	144,200
Travel Funds , additional contribution to the CLR fund which enables important foreign librarians to visit the United States when their presence is essential.	3,500
Travel Funds , additional contribution to the CLR fund which enables librarians and others whose work is important to libraries to attend important overseas meetings in which they have an essential role.	5,000
	<hr/>
	\$275,400

general

Each year the Council makes a few grants that fail to fit any of the rather specific categories included in this report. More often than not they assist in the financing of a special conference, the writing and/or editing of a book, or the compilation of statistics, all in fields related to libraries. Four such grants were made in 1974-75, and a previously funded project was completed.

University of Iowa Conference

A conference on "The Publication of American Historical Manuscripts" was held in the Herbert Hoover Presidential Library of the University of Iowa, April 30-May 1, with the assistance of the Council. It was attended by members of the National Historical Publications Commission, editors of forthcoming letterpress editions of the papers of outstanding Americans, curators of manuscript collections, and interested historians and librarians. The conference, which devoted its attention to past, present, and future efforts to make the papers of notable Americans available to students and scholars, was considered by its conveners to have been most constructive.

Library Planning and Federal Policy

Kathleen Molz, chief planning officer for library programs at the U. S. Office of Education until her resignation in 1974, sought and received CLR support in connection with preparation of a book tentatively titled "Federal Policy and Library Planning." It is hoped that the book will assist librarians who must deal with federal programs by increasing their awareness of the ways federal officials make decisions on planning and budgeting and on the administration of legislated programs.

Library Interiors Handbook

William S. Pierce of Pennsylvania State University was provided a small CLR grant this year to enable him to complete his already extensive travel and photography in connection with writing a book provisionally entitled "Planning the Library Interior: A Handbook." Mr. Pierce, whose responsibilities at Penn State have included library planning and furnishing, is conducting his travels during a six-month sabbatical leave. Marcel Dekker, Inc., has contracted to publish the book upon its completion.

Slide Libraries

Betty Jo Irvine's CLR-supported guide on slide libraries for academic institutions and museums has been published by Libraries Unlimited, Inc., of Littleton, Colorado, under the title *Slide Libraries*. Subject matter covered includes general background, administration and staffing, classification and cataloging, use of standard library techniques and tools, acquisition, production methods and techniques, projection sys-

tems, and miscellaneous equipment and supplies. There is also a selected bibliography of slide sources, slide libraries, and equipment manufacturers and distributors.

The following is a list of grants approved in fiscal 1975 of a general nature:

Milton O. Gustafson , toward attendance at meeting of Association for Asian Studies.	\$ 270
Indiana University Graduate Library School , to conduct statistical analyses of academic libraries and their relationships to characteristics of their host institutions, based on USOE computer tapes.	972
R. Kathleen Molz , for assistance with a projected book on library planning and federal policy.	8,000
William S. Pierce , for travel and photography expenses in connection with preparation of his book "Planning the Library Interior."	3,000
University of Iowa , partial support of conference on "The Publication of American Historical Manuscripts."	3,750
	\$15,992

(Certain contracts and grants have purposes that effectively serve several program areas and are allocated among them in the financial statement on page 54, a fact not reflected in the preceding narrative report on pages 8-41.)

PUBLICATIONS RESULTING FROM CLR-SUPPORTED PROGRAMS AND FELLOWSHIPS January 1, 1974-June 30, 1975

Part 1. Programs

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CLR-Supported Projects Active in Fiscal 1975

	Unpaid 6/30/74	Grant	FY 1975 Payment	Unpaid 6/30/75
ADMINISTRATION & MANAGEMENT				
RESEARCH ASSOCIATION OF NEW YORK CITY, INC.				
<i>Citizens' Information Centers</i> [\$300,000-1972]	\$ 265,000 ¹	\$ —	\$ —	\$ —
AMERICAN ASSOCIATION FOR STATE AND LOCAL HISTORY				
Nashville, Tenn.				
<i>Preparation of book on collection, care, and use of photographs</i> [\$10,000-1972]	8,300	—	2,800	5,500
<i>Preparation of manual on the collection and servicing of local history material</i> [\$34,604-1970]	6,430	—	3,750	2,680
AMERICAN ASSOCIATION OF LAW LIBRARIES, COMMITTEE ON STATISTICS, Washington, D. C.				
<i>Survey of U. S. and Canadian law library resources</i> [\$20,000-1968]	6,904	—	2,000	4,904
AMERICAN LIBRARY ASSOCIATION				
Chicago, Ill.				
<i>American Library Laws, receipts from sales of fourth edition supported production of a first supplement</i> [\$10,500-1962]	—	—	—	—
<i>Books for College Libraries</i> [\$290,502-1969; \$21,100-1973]	91,912	—	91,912	—
<i>Consumers' handbook for public libraries</i>	—	8,372	4,000	4,372
<i>Revision of Anglo-American Cataloging Rules</i>	—	111,431	50,000	61,431
AMERICAN SOCIETY FOR INFORMATION SCIENCE				
Washington, D. C.				
<i>Index to JASIS</i>	—	19,910	10,000	9,910
ETTA ARNTZEN, New York, N.Y.				
<i>Revision of Guide to Art Reference Books</i> [\$8,000-1971]	1,600	—	—	1,600
ASSOCIATION OF RESEARCH LIBRARIES, Washington, D. C.				
<i>Office of University Library Management Studies</i> [\$130,000-1973; \$81,136-1974]				
	104,505	210,000	82,731	231,774
PAUL N. BANKS, Chicago, Ill.				
<i>Assistance in writing a manual on library conservation; awaiting publication</i> [\$988-1974]	—	—	—	—

	Unpaid 6/30/74	FY 1975 Grant	Payment	Unpaid 6/30/75
W. J. BARROW RESEARCH LABORATORY, INC., Richmond, Va. <i>Research on preservation of books and other library materials</i> [\$150,633-1974]	\$ 44,864	\$ —	\$ 15,629 ²	\$ —
	—	240,000	122,722	117,278
BOSTON THEOLOGICAL INSTITUTE, Cambridge, Mass. <i>International Standard Serial Numbers for theological serials</i>	—	1,000	750	250
BUCKNELL UNIVERSITY Lewisburg, Pa. <i>Automated on-line retrieval system</i> [\$28,000-1973]	5,250	—	2,423 ²	—
ANTHONY CAINS, Dublin, Ireland <i>Completion of workshop manual on restoration of printed books and parchment manuscripts; awaiting publication</i> [\$4,350-1972]	—	—	—	—
COLLEGE ENTRANCE EXAMINATION BOARD, New York, N.Y. <i>Office of Library Independent Study and Guidance Projects</i> [\$100,000-1973; \$50,000-1974]	75,000	—	50,000	25,000
COLUMBIA UNIVERSITY New York, N.Y. <i>Library Planning Office</i> [\$126,308-1972]	36,308	—	26,800	9,508
COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS				
<i>Academic Library Development Program</i>	—	100,000	11,875	88,125
<i>U. of North Carolina, Charlotte</i> [\$47,046-1975]				
<i>Academic Library Management Intern Program</i> [\$100,000-1974]	94,114	265,000	115,553	243,561
<i>Advanced Study Program for Librarians</i>	—	115,000	305	114,695
<i>Valerie Bloomfield, to study significant private research libraries in England</i> [\$10,000-1974]	8,105	—	2,255	5,850
<i>Conversion of Serials program (CONSER)</i>	—	250,000	24,274	225,726
<i>Fellowship program</i> ³	96,652	72,823	63,823	86,056
<i>Microfiche Reader Testing Device project</i> [\$10,650-1973]	6,266	4,000	6,100	4,166
<i>National Bibliographic Control Advisory Group on National Bibliographic Control</i>	—	22,000	2,259	19,741

	Unpaid 6/30/74	Grant	FY 1975 Payment	Unpaid 6/30/75
<i>Joint CLR-NSF conference on national bibliographic control [\$4,275-1974]</i>	\$ 971	\$ —	\$ 544	\$ 427
<i>National bibliographic center feasibility study and initial pilot program [\$60,000-1974]</i>	44,232	—	22,679 ²	—
<i>Travel fund for foreign librarians to visit the U. S. [\$5,000-1972; \$3,000-1974]</i>	1,765	3,500	—	5,265
<i>Travel fund for U. S. librarians to attend meetings abroad [\$5,000-1970]</i>	3,141	5,000	5,254 ²	2,806
EARLHAM COLLEGE, Richmond, Ind. <i>Column on periodicals for Choice magazine</i>	—	7,500	2,300	5,200
EASTERN MICHIGAN UNIVERSITY Ypsilanti, Mich. <i>Project LOEX</i>	—	41,969	3,400	38,569
DR. HANS-PETER GEH Stuttgart, Germany <i>Study tour of U. S. libraries</i>	—	3,500	2,129 ²	—
GOVERNORS STATE UNIVERSITY Park Forest South, Ill. <i>Selective dissemination of micro- fiche documents [\$5,138-1973]</i>	2,338	—	1,400	938
DR. MILTON O. GUSTAFSON Washington, D. C. <i>Toward attendance at meeting of Association for Asian Studies</i>	—	270	270	—
MARGARET HEY, Rome, Italy <i>Investigation of book and archival restoration techniques [\$10,500-1972]</i>	493	—	209 ²	—
INDIANA UNIVERSITY, GRADUATE LIBRARY SCHOOL, Bloomington, Ind. <i>Analysis of library statistics</i>	—	972	972	—
INTERNATIONAL ASSOCIATION OF LAW LIBRARIES, Marburg/L., Germany <i>To enable five law librarians from developing countries to attend its 5th International Course in Law Librarianship [\$2,500-1974]</i>	2,500	—	2,500	—
INTERNATIONAL COUNCIL ON ARCHIVES, Paris, France <i>ICA Secretariat</i>	—	72,000	5,500	66,500
INTERNATIONAL FEDERATION FOR DOCUMENTATION, The Hague, Netherlands				

	Unpaid 6/30/74	Grant	FY 1975 Payment	Unpaid 6/30/75
<i>Support for Executive Committee meeting, Washington, D. C. [\$1,680-1974]</i>	\$ 1,680	\$ —	\$ 720 ²	\$ —
INTERNATIONAL FEDERATION OF LIBRARY ASSOCIATIONS (IFLA)				
The Hague, Netherlands				
<i>Establishment of a permanent secretariat for the Committee on Cataloguing [\$54,000-1974]</i>	3,600	—	3,600	—
<i>IFLA general secretariat [\$45,000-1974]</i>	25,399	45,000	43,956	26,443
<i>Office for Universal Bibliographic Control [\$70,000-1974]</i>	70,000	144,200	64,000	150,200
DR. DONALD M. JACOBS				
Boston, Mass.				
<i>Index of black newspapers published prior to the Civil War</i>	—	500	400	100
LIBRARY OF CONGRESS				
Washington, D. C.				
<i>Feasibility study on LC as a national bibliographic center</i>	—	94,632	27,000	67,632
<i>Study to determine hardware and software needs of a national bibliographic service</i>	—	6,500	5,000	1,500
<i>National union catalog format study</i>	—	5,000	2,000	3,000
<i>Equipment for Preservation Research Office [\$95,000-1970]</i>	25,000 ²	—	—	—
MICHIGAN STATE UNIVERSITY				
East Lansing, Mich.				
<i>Directory of university extension library services at National University Extension Association and National Association of State Universities and Land Grant Colleges member institutions [\$1,602-1971]</i>	402	—	—	402
R. KATHLEEN MOLZ, Washington, D. C.				
<i>Preparation of a book on federal policy and library planning</i>	—	8,000	4,000	4,000
NATIONAL BOOK COMMITTEE, INC.				
New York, N.Y.				
<i>Conference on role of library services and educational materials in educational programs of developing countries [\$9,000-1973]</i>	2,500	—	2,500	—
<i>Conference to examine the effect of changes in public policy on the availability of books in the U. S. [\$5,000-1973]</i>	2,000	—	764 ²	—

	Unpaid 6/30/74	FY 1975 Grant	Payment	Unpaid 6/30/75
NATIONAL ENDOWMENT FOR THE HUMANITIES, Washington, D. C.				
<i>Continuation of College Library Program (matching grant)</i>	\$ -	\$ 100,000	\$ 100,000	\$ -
<i>Preparation by Patricia K. Grimstead of book entitled "Regional Archives and Manuscript Repositories in the USSR: A Directory and Bibliography of Published Reference Aids;" awaiting publication (matching grant) [\$12,739-1971]</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>To speed the work at LC in developing a national serials data base in the humanities in machine-readable form (matching grant)</i>	-	118,600	118,600	-
NEW ENGLAND INTERSTATE LIBRARY COMPACT, Hartford, Conn.				
<i>New England Document Conservation Center [\$70,000-1973]</i>	31,800	-	31,800	-
OHIO COLLEGE LIBRARY CENTER, Columbus, Ohio				
<i>Further development of OCLC's computerized regional library system [\$194,000-1973]</i>	24,000	-	24,000	-
<i>Development of additional subsystems at OCLC</i>	-	124,250	45,000	79,250
WILLIAM S. PIERCE, State College, Pa.				
<i>Preparation of a book on planning the library interior</i>	-	3,000	-	3,000
SOUTHEASTERN LIBRARY NETWORK (SOLINET), Atlanta, Ga.				
<i>Program to train librarians to participate in the SOLINET system [\$10,000-1974]</i>	10,000	-	6,600	3,400
SOUTHWESTERN LIBRARY ASSOCIATION, Dallas, Tex.				
<i>Development of the Southwestern Library Interstate Cooperative Endeavor (SLICE) [\$50,000-1973]</i>	26,800	-	26,800	-
STANFORD UNIVERSITY, Stanford, Calif.				
<i>Further support of BALLOTS implementation</i>	-	348,800	105,000	243,800
UNESCO, Division of Scientific and Technological Information and Documentation, Paris, France				
<i>UNISIST/IFID/IFLA international summer school for teachers and workers in the information field</i>	-	2,200	2,200	-

	Unpaid 6/30/74	FY 1975 Grant	Payment	Unpaid 6/30/75
UNIVERSITY OF CHICAGO, Chicago, Ill. <i>For completion of the library data management system</i>	\$ —	\$ 350,000	\$ 100,000	\$ 250,000
UNIVERSITY OF CHICAGO, GRADUATE LIBRARY SCHOOL Chicago, Ill. <i>Fellowship program for holders of nonlibrary Ph.D. degrees [\$103,000-1974]</i>	68,800	—	31,200	37,600
UNIVERSITY OF IOWA, Iowa City, Ia. <i>Conference on the publication of American historical manuscripts</i>	—	3,750	2,519	1,231
UNIVERSITY OF LANCASTER Lancaster, England <i>Research on factors affecting the use of library services</i>	6,000	—	4,958 ²	—
UNIVERSITY OF NORTH CAROLINA Chapel Hill, N.C. <i>Administration of American National Standards Institute (ANSI) Committee Z39 [\$14,000-1974]</i>	14,000	14,000	17,000	11,000
UNIVERSITY OF THE STATE OF NEW YORK, Albany, N.Y. (for the New York State Library) <i>Study of state government information needs [\$25,000-1974]</i>	25,000	—	21,000	4,000
VANDERBILT UNIVERSITY Nashville, Tenn. (on behalf of the Joint University Libraries) <i>Establishment of a model research and development unit [\$171,107-1969; \$89,475-1972]</i>	109,010	—	53,250	55,760
WABASH COLLEGE Crawfordsville, Ind. <i>For its College Library Program (matching grant) [\$50,000-1970]</i>	15,000	—	10,000	5,000
WESTERN INTERSTATE COMMISSION FOR HIGHER EDUCATION (WICHE) Boulder, Colo. <i>Design and development of a western interstate bibliographic network</i>	—	79,325	17,500	61,825
Grants Payable	\$1,367,641			
Adjustments ¹⁻²	368,185			
Totals	\$ 999,456	\$3,002,004	\$1,610,485	\$2,390,975

¹ Council commitment withdrawn (see p. 34).

² Unused portion of grants payable returned to funds.

³ Amount appropriated each year according to individual budgets of fellowships awarded.

Opinion of Independent Accountants

August 27, 1975

To the Board of Directors of
Council on Library Resources, Inc.

We have examined the balance sheet of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. as of June 30, 1975 and the related statements of support, revenue, and expenses and changes in fund balance, of functional expenses and of changes in cash and investments for the year then ended. Our examination was made in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards, and accordingly included such tests of the accounting records and such other auditing procedures as we considered necessary in the circumstances.

As of July 1, 1975 the Council on Library Resources, Inc. changed its method of accounting for grant revenue, as described in Note 2 to the financial statements.

In our opinion, the financial statements examined by us present fairly the financial position of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. at June 30, 1975, and the results of its operations and changes in fund balance and the changes in cash and investments for the year then ended, in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles, which, except for the change referred to in the preceding paragraph, with which we concur, have been applied on a basis consistent with that of the preceding year.

PRICE WATERHOUSE & CO.

Balance Sheet, June 30, 1975

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

ASSETS

Cash	\$ 290,785
Investments	
Savings account	4,401
Certificates of deposit, at cost	1,400,000
Accrued interest	13,476
Accrued royalties (Note 3)	3,395
Grant receivable from The Ford Foundation (Note 2)	4,130,000
Other receivables	22,000
Prepaid expenses and deposits	9,210
	<u>\$5,873,267</u>

LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE

Grants and contracts payable	\$2,304,919
Co-sponsored grants payable	24,228
Fellowships payable	86,056
Deferred income from Ford Foundation grant (Note 2)	4,130,000
Accounts payable and accrued salaries, taxes and employee benefits	33,010
Fund balance (Note 4)	(704,946)
	<u>\$5,873,267</u>

Statement of Support, Income and Expenses and Changes in Fund Balance

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

For the Year Ended June 30, 1975

SUPPORT AND REVENUE	
Grant from Ford Foundation (Note 2)	\$1,870,000
Income from investments	122,685
Income from royalties	6,007
Total support and revenue	<u>1,998,692</u>
EXPENSES	
Program	
Automation, networks, standardization, and national library services	1,536,004
Libraries and their users	115,525
Management	323,137
Microforms	24,059
Preservation	109,977
Professional development	460,923
International activities	282,222
General	52,136
Total program expenses	<u>2,903,983</u>
Administrative	
Compensation and employee benefits	136,699
Travel and meetings	13,361
Audit and legal fees	8,121
Rent (Note 5)	29,738
Equipment rental and furniture	4,332
Printing and duplication	9,302
Office and other expenses	25,703
Total administrative expenses	<u>227,256</u>
Total expenses	<u>3,131,239</u>
EXCESS OF EXPENSES OVER SUPPORT AND REVENUE	
Fund balance, beginning of year	(1,132,547)
Fund balance, end of year	<u>427,601</u>
	<u>\$ (704,946)</u>

Statement of Changes in Cash and Investments

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

For the Year Ended June 30, 1975

CASH RECEIPTS	
Receipts from the Ford Foundation	\$1,870,000
Receipts from co-sponsors	11,300
Income from investments and royalties	124,726
Grant and fellowship refunds	3,650
	<u>2,009,676</u>
CASH DISBURSEMENTS	
Program expense	1,886,262
Administrative expense	245,696
	<u>2,131,958</u>
EXCESS OF CASH DISBURSEMENTS OVER CASH RECEIPTS	
	(122,282)
Increase in accrued interest	3,504
Cash and investments, beginning of year	1,827,440
Cash and investments, end of year	<u><u>\$1,708,662</u></u>

STATEMENT OF FUNCTIONAL EXPENDITURES FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 1975

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

	Automation, networks, standardization, and national library services	Libraries and their users	Management	Microforms	Preservation	Professional development	International	General	Total	Administrative	Total
Grants and contracts	\$1,645,538	\$103,251	\$310,000	\$ 4,000	\$120,000	\$385,270	\$270,400	\$90,722	\$2,929,181		\$2,929,181
Fellowships						72,823			72,823		72,823
Less: Adjustments resulting from excess allocations of grants and fellowships	(259,830)				(39,902)	(19,596)	(3,373)	(45,484)	(368,185)		(368,185)
	<u>1,385,708</u>	<u>103,251</u>	<u>310,000</u>	<u>4,000</u>	<u>80,098</u>	<u>438,497</u>	<u>267,027</u>	<u>45,238</u>	<u>2,633,819</u>		<u>2,633,819</u>
Compensation and employee benefits	123,730	9,050	11,529	19,609	28,723	18,992	11,549	6,546	229,728	\$136,699	366,427
Consultant fees	7,122	1,410	80	150		140	2,558	40	11,500		11,500
Travel and meetings	14,807	1,809	1,522	223	1,102	3,273	1,082	309	24,127	13,361	37,488
Other	4,637	5	6	77	54	21	6	3	4,809		4,809
Audit and legal fees										8,121	8,121
Rent										29,738	29,738
Equipment rental and furniture										4,332	4,332
Printing and duplication										9,302	9,302
Office and other expenses										25,703	25,703
	<u>\$1,536,004</u>	<u>\$115,525</u>	<u>\$323,137</u>	<u>\$24,059</u>	<u>\$109,977</u>	<u>\$460,923</u>	<u>\$282,222</u>	<u>\$52,136</u>	<u>\$2,903,983</u>	<u>\$227,256</u>	<u>\$3,131,239</u>

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS
JUNE 30, 1975

1. Organization

The Council on Library Resources is a non-profit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1956 for the purpose of promoting library research. The Council's operations are financed through grants from the Ford Foundation. Effective July 1, 1974 the Council received a new grant of \$6,000,000 for continuation of its program. The grant agreement specifies that the grant funds received are to be disbursed in substantial compliance with an annual budget of approximately \$2,000,000 for the three year grant period.

The Council is a private operating foundation and is exempt from Federal income tax under Internal Revenue code section 501 (c)(3).

2. Summary of Significant Accounting Policies

Basis of Accounting. The Council on Library Resources maintains its accounting records on the accrual basis of accounting. Royalty revenue is accrued as the related publications are sold. Grants and fellowships are recorded as an expense in the year in which the applicable grant or fellowship agreement is entered into. Purchases of office furniture and equipment are recorded as an expense in the year acquired.

Change in Accounting Method. Effective July 1, 1974 the Council changed its method of accounting for the grant from the Ford Foundation. In prior years, the full amount of the grant was taken directly into fund balance in the initial year of the grant. The new method recognizes revenue over the term of the grant on the basis of budgeted payments from Ford. The balance of grant funds, recorded as receivable, are deferred to future periods. The new method was adopted to provide a better matching of revenues and expenses. The change in method has no effect on the beginning fund balance since under either method total revenue from the previous three-year grant would have been fully recognized at June 30, 1974.

3. Royalties

The Council receives royalties from the sale of a publication entitled, "Handbook of Data Processing for Libraries." These royalties are being used to fund the preparation of a revision and supplement to this work. The Council also receives royalties under an agreement relating to the publication and sale of a book entitled, "Economics of Academic Libraries." Both of these publications were developed under the Council's sponsorship.

4. Appropriation of Funds

At June 30, 1975, \$114,000 had been appropriated by the Board of Directors for specific grants and contracts. In addition, \$77,100 had been allocated for future grants and contracts up to \$25,000 or additions to existing grants and contracts of up to \$5,000 each, to be made at the President's discretion.

5. Commitments

The Council leases office space under a lease expiring November 30, 1977 providing for minimum annual rentals of approximately \$30,500.

Index

- Administration and Management Research
 Association of New York City, Inc. 34, 44
American Association for State and Local
 History 44
American Association of Law Libraries 44
American Library Association 12, 16, 33, 44
American National Standards Institute's
 Committee Z-39 10, 12, 49
American Society for Information Science
 35, 44
Arntzen, Etta 44
Association of Research Library 24-25,44
Banks, Paul 44
Barrow, W. J. Research Laboratory, Inc. 28, 45
Boston Theological Institute 16, 45
Bucknell University 15, 45
Cains, Anthony 29, 45
Clark College 31
CLR-administered programs:
 Academic Library Development Program
 25-26, 45
 Academic Library Management Intern
 Program 18-19, 45
 Advanced Study Program for Librarians
 18, 45
 Advisory Group on National Bibliographic
 Control 10, 46
 Bloomfield, Valerie 45
 College Library Program 31-32,48
 Conversion of Serials (CONSER) Program
 10, 45
 Fellowship Program 19-21, 45
 Joint CLR-NSF Conference on National
 Bibliographic Control 9, 46
 Microfiche Reader Testing Device 28, 46
 National Bibliographic Center 11, 46
 Travel Funds for Foreign Librarians 46
 Travel Funds for U. S. Librarians 46
College Entrance Examination Board 34, 45
Columbia University 25, 45
Earlham College 33, 46
Eastern Michigan University 32-33, 46
Geh, Hans-Peter 39, 46
Governors State University 46
Gustafson, Milton O. 46
Hey, Margaret 29, 46
Indiana University Graduate Library School
 40, 46
International Association of Law Librarians 46
International Council on Archives 38, 46
International Federation for Documentation 47
International Federation of Library Associations
 36-38, 47
Irvine, Betty Jo 40
Jacobs, Donald M. 36, 47
Joint University Libraries 25, 49
Kearney State College 32
Library of Congress 11, 12, 28, 47
Los Angeles Public Library 34
Michigan State University 47
Mills College 32
Molz, R. Kathleen 40, 48
National Book Committee 47
National Endowment for the Humanities
 31, 36, 48
New England Interstate Library Compact
 28-29, 48
Ohio College Library Center 13-14, 48
Pacific University 32
Pierce, William S. 40, 48
Southeastern Library Network 14, 48
Southwestern Library Association 15, 48
Stanford University 14, 48
Unesco 38-39, 49
University of Chicago 15, 49
University of Chicago Graduate Library School
 18, 49
University of Iowa 40, 49
University of Kentucky 32
University of Lancaster (England) 49
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill 12, 49
University of North Carolina at Charlotte 26, 45
University of the State of New York 35, 49
University of Utah 32
Vanderbilt University 49
Wabash College 49
Western Interstate Commission for Higher
 Education 13, 49

Acknowledgements

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